

SUPPLEMENTARY DOCUMENTS

Supplementary document 4. Morphometric parameters of the maternal aortic arch in pregnant rats exposed to filtered (FA) or non-filtered air (NFA) during pregestational and gestational periods. Data are expressed as median (interquartile range, IQR: 25th–75th percentiles). Group comparisons were performed using the Kruskal–Wallis (KW) test followed by Dunn's post hoc test with adjustment for multiple comparisons, using FA/FA as reference group. Statistical significance: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$; **** $p < 0.0001$; ns, not significant.

Variable	FA/FA	FA/NFA	NFA/FA	NFA/NFA	KW p	Dunn's post hoc (vs FA/FA)
<i>Tunica intima</i> (μm)	5.2 (3.8–7.3)	5.8 (4.1–11)	5.3 (4.7–6.0)	4.7 (3.6–6.0)	0.0995	ns (all)
<i>Tunica media</i> (μm)	128 (103–158)	116 (65–130)	115 (96–129)	106 (83–118)	0.0251*	FA/FA vs NFA/NFA: $p = 0.0094^{**}$ FA/FA vs FA/NFA: ns FA/FA vs NFA/FA: ns
<i>Tunica adventitia</i> (μm)	105 (54–163)	46 (33–84)	81 (60–122)	50 (18–85)	0.0014* *	FA/FA vs FA/NFA: $p = 0.0083^{**}$ FA/FA vs NFA/NFA: $p = 0.0042^{**}$ FA/FA vs NFA/FA: ns
<i>Elastic fiber density</i> ($n/10,000 \mu\text{m}^2$)	12 (11–12)	12 (9–13)	15 (11–18)	12 (6–13)	0.0038* *	FA/FA vs NFA/FA: $p = 0.0138^*$ FA/FA vs FA/NFA: ns FA/FA vs NFA/NFA: ns
<i>Inter-elastic fiber distance</i> (μm)	6.7 (4.5–9.6)	5.4 (3.7–7.5)	5.0 (3.2–7.6)	5.4 (3.7–7.8)	<0.0001 ****	FA/FA vs FA/NFA: $p < 0.0001^{****}$ FA/FA vs NFA/FA: $p < 0.0001^{****}$ FA/FA vs NFA/NFA: $p = 0.0002^{***}$